

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

DATAMITE has passed the halfway point of the project

Editorial by the project coordinator, **Santiago Cáceres**.

With an eye on the feedback received during the mid-term review meeting with the European Commission and on achieving our main objective by the end of 2025, **Santiago Cáceres**, project coordinator, talks about the achievements so far, but above all about **the roadmap for transforming theory into practice**.

Editorial by the technical coordinator, **Jordi Arjona**.

JORDI ARJONA

TECHNICAL COORDINATOR

Jordi Arjona, technical coordinator of DATAMITE, explains in this editorial the **current state of the project from a technical point of view** and previews the areas of work on which the second half of the project will focus.

International events

DATAMITE at the European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) 2024

The European [Big Data Value Forum \(EBDVF\) 2024](#) took place from 2 to 4 October in Budapest, Hungary. The event, organised by the [Big Data Value Association](#) (BDVA), brings together industry professionals, business

developers, researchers and policy-makers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to **advance policy actions, and industrial and research activities** in the areas of Data and AI.

For the [second year in a row](#), **DATAMITE** was present during the three days of the forum. This year, with a twist, it did so as **part of the EUDATA+ cluster** that brings together six Horizon Europe projects ([enRichMyData](#), [UPCAST](#), [PISTIS](#), [Graph-Massivizer](#), [FAME](#) and [DATAMITE](#)) to create synergies that revolutionise data monetisation. The cluster **participated in EBDVF with a 6-square-metre booth and a 2-hour session.**

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DATAMITE at OCX and eSAAM 2024

The Open Community Experience 2024 ([OCX](#)), hosted by the [Eclipse Foundation](#) was held from 22 to 24 October in Mainz, Germany. **DATAMITE** has been **represented during the three days of the event** thanks to the Eclipse booth.

OCX organises several collocated events, including [eSAAM](#). The 4th **Eclipse Security, Artificial Intelligence, Architecture, and Modelling Conference on DATA SPACES**, took place during the first day, Tuesday 22, and **DATAMITE participated in two ways**. On the one hand as a proud sponsor of the conference, and on the other hand with Publication presentations by two of the consortium members within the 'architecture block'.

DATAMITE at Enlit Europe 2024

[Enlit Europe](#), one of the biggest EU energy events, was held from 22 to 24 October in Milan, Italy. The conference attracts 15,000 visitors, brings together more than 700 exhibiting companies, over 80 thematic sessions and more than 100 EU-funded projects, and features 500 speakers. Thanks to our [energy use cases](#), led by our partners E-REDES and HEDNO, **DATAMITE has been a perfect match for Enlit Europe 2024.**

E-REDES and Hedno brought **DATAMITE** to Enlit Europe with a **booth located at the EU Projects Zone**. And, Ricardo Almeida Henriques (E-REDES) had the opportunity to present **DATAMITE** in the session 'Energy efficiency and optimisation with digital technologies'.

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Eclipse Dataspace Components and DATAMITE

On the 8th of October, DATAMITE had the pleasure to participate in the second episode of the [Eclipse](#) webinar series 'Research meets Open Source'. The webinar featured two talks: 'New concepts for cross-company data sharing: Eclipse Dataspace Components', by **Markus Spiekermann** from **Huawei Technologies** and 'DATAMITE: An open-source framework to enable data monetisation' by **Jordi Arjona**, **DATAMITE** technical coordinator, from ITI.

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DATAMITE presence at EGI 2024

[EGI 2024](#), the conference that brings together international scientific communities, IT and service providers, European projects, security experts, community managers and policy makers **to address data research and innovation**, was held from 30 September to 4 October in Lecce, Italy.

DATAMITE did not miss the opportunity to be **present at this important date**, thanks to its member of the consortium, [EGI](#).

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E-REDES Business Exploitation Workshop

On 25th September, [E-REDES](#), DATAMITE use case provider, organised a Business Exploitation Workshop in Lisbon. The main objective of the workshop was to **showcase the progress made** on the [E-REDES DATAMITE pilot](#) during the first reporting period of DATAMITE.

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AGRO SHOW 2024 involving DATAMITE

AGRO SHOW, the largest open-air agricultural exhibition in Europe, was held from 20 to 22 September 2024 in Bednary, Poland.

The Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC) – one of DATAMITE's agricultural use case providers – represented the project.

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DATAMITE at IEEE COINS 2024

The IEEE International Conference on Omni-layer Intelligent systems (COINS) 2024 was held from 29 to 31 July. One of this year's vertical tracks discussed during the conference was 'smart agriculture, and DATAMITE played a leading role in the discussions on this topic thanks to the Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center.

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Discover the DATAMITE Open Source Repository

We are pleased to announce the **DATAMITE open source repository** developed by the DATAMITE partners and hosted at [Eclipse Research Labs](#). As part of DATAMITE's commitment to open science, and advocating for interoperability and openness, the DATAMITE Framework is provided as open source **software and is available in its public repository**.

The **DATAMITE** open source repository, hosted at Eclipse Research Labs in Gitlab, is the maximum exponent of the project's commitment to open science in all its aspects, and joins other open repositories such as [Zenodo](#), which hosts all the publications written in the context of DATAMITE. Thus, DATAMITE has an **Open Source Code Repository and an Open Access Research Repository**.

The DATAMITE open source repository has **eight sub-repositories** to make navigation as easy and understandable as possible. These repositories are:

- Data-governance.
- Data-quality.
- Data-security.
- Data-Sharing.
- Data-support-tools.
- Docs.
- Fronted
- IP-analysis.

[Access the repository](#)

Upcoming events

The DATAMITE consortium partners are constantly working to showcase the progress of the project, presenting the latest publications and articles at various national and international events. Here is a list of **events not to be missed between November and December 2024**.

[Check the upcoming event list](#)

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